

Benign Multicystic Peritoneal Mesothelioma Mimicking Acute Appendicitis: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Background: Benign multicystic peritoneal mesothelioma is a rare tumor derived from mesothelial cells characterized by multiple thin-walled cysts attached to the peritoneal surfaces. It occurs more frequently in women and has been associated with previous abdominal surgery, endometriosis, or pelvic inflammatory disease. Despite its benign nature, it has a high recurrence rate after surgical treatment.

Case presentation: We report the case of a 34-year-old male with a history of bilateral varicocelectomy and bilateral inguinal hernioplasty who presented to the emergency department with acute onset right lower quadrant abdominal pain suggestive of acute appendicitis. Laboratory tests showed elevated C-reactive protein levels. Abdominal computed tomography revealed multiple well-defined cystic lesions in the right lower abdomen and pelvis. Diagnostic laparoscopy was performed due to suspicion of a periappendiceal abscess, revealing a 6 × 4 × 2 cm multicystic tumor attached to the mesentery and right colon, along with multiple grape-like cystic lesions throughout the abdominal cavity. Local tumor resection, removal of most cystic lesions, and appendectomy were performed. Histopathological examination confirmed the diagnosis of benign multicystic peritoneal mesothelioma.

Conclusion: This case highlights an uncommon presentation of benign multicystic peritoneal mesothelioma in a male patient mimicking acute appendicitis. Laparoscopy plays an important role in both diagnosis and treatment, allowing complete surgical resection. Long-term follow-up is recommended due to the risk of recurrence.

KEYWORDS: Benign multicystic peritoneal mesothelioma, Peritoneal mesothelioma, Acute abdomen, Appendicitis mimic, Laparoscopy, Case report.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Benign multicystic peritoneal mesothelioma is a rare tumor derived from mesothelial cells and is characterized by the presence of multiple cysts attached to the abdominal or pelvic cavity. (2) Its etiology remains unknown. It occurs more frequently in women and has been associated with a history of abdominal surgery, endometriosis, or pelvic inflammatory disease, suggesting a possible reactive origin. (1)

Mesotheliomas most commonly arise in the pleura (60–80%), followed by the peritoneum (15%) and the pericardium (10%). Three main types have been described, with benign multicystic peritoneal mesothelioma being the least common but notable for its recurrent behavior. (1)

Three types of peritoneal mesotheliomas have been described:

- Benign adenomatoid mesothelioma (most common): Most cases are asymptomatic and are usually discovered incidentally during laparotomy or laparoscopy.
- Benign multicystic peritoneal mesothelioma (least common): Although benign, it is characterized by a tendency for recurrence.
- Malignant peritoneal mesothelioma (10–25%): This type predominantly affects men between the fifth and sixth decades of life and has been associated with asbestos

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exposure. The median survival is approximately 6–10 months. (1)

Clinical manifestations are usually nonspecific and may include abdominal pain, palpable abdominal mass, fever, urinary symptoms, and abdominal distension, sometimes mimicking acute appendicitis. (3)

Imaging studies such as abdominal ultrasound, computed tomography (CT), or magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) can help identify intra-abdominal cystic lesions. However, the definitive diagnosis is usually established during surgical exploration, where a multicystic mass adjacent to the cecum or periappendiceal region may be identified, consisting of translucent cystic lesions lined by flat, cuboidal, or papillary mesothelial cells. (3) Histopathological examination and immunohistochemical analysis confirm the diagnosis by

demonstrating the characteristic microvilli of mesothelial cells. (1)

The treatment of choice is complete surgical resection of the lesions. Chemotherapy and radiotherapy have not shown benefit in the management of this condition. Recurrence rates range from 25% to 50%, frequently requiring repeat surgical intervention. (1)

The increasing use of laparoscopy to identify pathological causes of lower abdominal pain of unclear origin has improved the recognition and management of this tumor. (4) No specific risk factors for recurrence have been clearly identified; however, recurrence has been associated primarily with incomplete surgical resection of the lesions. To date, no cases of metastasis or malignant transformation have been reported. (5)

Figure 1. A) Multicystic tumor with a grape-like appearance, 6x4x2 cm. B) Multiple cystic lesions resembling "grape clusters". C) Lobulated cystic lesions.

Long-term follow-up data for these patients remain limited; therefore, the overall prognosis is still uncertain.

II. CASE REPORT

A 34-year-old male patient with a surgical history of bilateral varicocelectomy and bilateral inguinal hernia repair with mesh placement presented to the emergency department. These antecedents were considered relevant to the current condition. The patient reported the onset of symptoms one day prior to admission, characterized by sudden stabbing abdominal pain predominantly located in the right lower quadrant, with an intensity of 10/10 on the numeric pain rating scale. No aggravating or relieving factors were identified. Dunphy's sign was positive. The patient denied nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, or fever and reported no previous similar episodes.

On physical examination, the patient was normotensive, with heart rate and respiratory rate within normal limits, oxygen saturation of 97%, and a body temperature of 37.2 °C. Neurological examination was normal, and no respiratory or cardiopulmonary abnormalities were identified. Abdominal examination revealed a flat, soft, and depressible abdomen with decreased bowel sounds. There was generalized tenderness to deep palpation, more pronounced in the right lower quadrant. Percussion revealed generalized tympany. McBurney's sign, rebound tenderness, and Dunphy's sign were positive. The extremities showed adequate capillary

refill. The patient weighed 74 kg and had a height of 183 cm, with a body mass index (BMI) of 22.1 kg/m².

Laboratory evaluation, including complete blood count and blood chemistry tests, revealed an elevated C-reactive protein level of 31 mg/L. A contrast-enhanced abdominal computed tomography (CT) scan was subsequently performed. The imaging study demonstrated a well-defined lobulated lesion with thin walls in the right flank, showing contrast enhancement without changes in internal density. In the right iliac fossa, well-circumscribed lobulated cystic lesions measuring 27 × 21 mm and 36 × 28 mm (the largest) were identified, with hypodense content (7 Hounsfield units) and thin walls. These findings were associated with surrounding fat stranding and free fluid extending from the perirenal space, respecting the right fascia, down to the pelvic cul-de-sac. Within the pelvic cul-de-sac, a thin-walled lobulated cystic lesion measuring 45 × 29 mm was also observed. Given the suspicion of a periappendiceal abscess, the patient underwent diagnostic laparoscopy. Intraoperatively, a 6 × 4 × 2 cm multicystic tumor with a grape-like appearance was identified arising from the mesentery and adherent to the right colon (Fig. 1). In addition, multiple cystic lesions resembling "grape clusters" were observed distributed throughout the abdominal cavity. The appendix appeared congested. Local resection of the periappendiceal tumor, removal of most of the cystic lesions attached to the abdominal cavity, and appendectomy were performed.

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III. RESULTS

Histopathological analysis of the specimen confirmed the diagnosis of benign multicystic peritoneal mesothelioma. The histological examination described a cecal appendix measuring 7×0.6 cm with fibrinopurulent adhesions and a congestive appearance. Two multicystic fragments measuring $6 \times 4 \times 2$ cm in total were identified. These fragments were lobulated, gray-violet in color, and had an edematous appearance. On sectioning, citrine-colored fluid was released, and the internal surface appeared smooth. The average wall thickness was 0.1 cm.

Microscopically, the cysts were lined by a single layer of cuboidal or low columnar epithelium supported by connective tissue containing capillary vessels. No lymphoid nodules or smooth muscle tissue were observed (Fig. 2).

Postoperative follow-up was performed to evaluate the patient's clinical evolution and to ensure the absence of complications related to the surgical procedure. The patient did not present intraoperative or immediate postoperative complications. Continued clinical follow-up will be carried out to monitor the patient's evolution and to detect any signs of recurrence or late complications.

IV. DISCUSSION

Benign multicystic peritoneal mesothelioma is a rare neoplasm derived from mesothelial cells of the peritoneum, characterized by the presence of multiple thin-walled cysts that may be distributed across different peritoneal surfaces. Most cases reported in the literature occur in women of reproductive age and have been associated with a history of previous abdominal surgery, endometriosis, or pelvic inflammatory disease, which has led to the hypothesis of a reactive etiology secondary to chronic peritoneal irritation. However, its pathogenesis remains controversial, as some authors consider it a true neoplastic lesion due to its recurrent behavior.

In the present case, the diagnosis was particularly unusual because the patient was a young male. Although most reports describe a female predominance, sporadic cases have been documented in male patients, generally associated with a history of prior abdominal surgery. In our patient, a history of bilateral varicocelectomy and bilateral inguinal hernia repair with mesh placement was identified, which may have

contributed to an inflammatory or reactive peritoneal process, favoring the development of this lesion.

From a clinical perspective, benign multicystic peritoneal mesothelioma may present with nonspecific symptoms such as abdominal pain, abdominal distension, or the presence of a palpable abdominal mass. In many cases, it is discovered incidentally during surgical procedures performed for other indications. In the present case, the clinical presentation mimicked an acute abdomen compatible with acute appendicitis, with right lower quadrant pain and signs of peritoneal irritation. This type of presentation has been described in some reports, where the periappendicular location of the lesions may lead to diagnostic confusion with inflammatory processes of the appendix.

Imaging studies, particularly computed tomography, can help identify these lesions. However, the findings are not specific, and the definitive diagnosis is usually established during surgical exploration and confirmed by histopathological examination. In this case, diagnostic laparoscopy allowed the identification of multiple cystic lesions with a "grape-like cluster" appearance distributed throughout the abdominal cavity, a characteristic finding described in this condition.

Histopathological examination confirmed the diagnosis by demonstrating cysts lined by a single layer of cuboidal or low columnar mesothelial epithelium supported by a vascularized connective tissue stroma, without evidence of cellular atypia or infiltration, findings consistent with benign multicystic peritoneal mesothelioma. Immunohistochemistry may be useful to confirm the mesothelial origin of the cells through specific markers, although in many cases the diagnosis can be established based on the typical histological features.

The treatment of choice for this entity is complete surgical resection of the lesions, as neither chemotherapy nor radiotherapy has demonstrated effectiveness in the management of this tumor. In the present case, resection of the main mesenteric lesion, removal of most of the visible cystic lesions, and appendectomy were performed, which resolved the patient's clinical condition. Despite its benign nature, this entity is characterized by a relatively high recurrence rate, reported between 25% and 50% of cases, mainly associated with incomplete resections or the presence of multiple peritoneal implants.

Due to the rarity of this pathology, the available information regarding its long-term evolution is limited, and reports of

Figure 2. A) Cysts were lined by a single layer of cuboidal or low columnar epithelium. B) Supported by connective tissue containing capillary vessels

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prolonged follow-up are scarce. Nevertheless, to date, no malignant transformation or metastasis associated with this entity has been documented. For this reason, periodic clinical follow-up is recommended for surgically treated patients in order to detect possible recurrences early and consider repeat surgical resection if necessary.

This case contributes to the existing literature by describing an uncommon presentation of benign multicystic peritoneal mesothelioma in a male patient with a clinical picture suggestive of acute appendicitis. Furthermore, it highlights the importance of considering this entity in the differential diagnosis of peritoneal cystic lesions and periappendicular masses, as well as the role of laparoscopy in both the diagnosis and treatment of this condition.

V. CONCLUSION

Benign multicystic peritoneal mesothelioma is a rare entity that may present with symptoms similar to those of acute appendicitis. The severity of symptoms is related to the size and location of the cysts.

The diagnostic approach should include laboratory and imaging studies in order to identify the inflammatory response and visualize cystic lesions. Laparoscopic surgical intervention represents the most effective therapeutic option, as it allows complete resection of the lesions while providing a less invasive approach and faster recovery.

It is important to emphasize the need for short- and medium-term follow-up in patients with benign multicystic peritoneal mesothelioma, even after successful surgical resection, due to the risk of recurrence.

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